

Annals of Quedlinburg

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Entry tags: Christianity, Catholic, Religious Group, Latin Text, Text, Chronicle, Medieval Christianity, Western Medieval text

The Annals of Quedlinburg, written at Quedlinburg Abbey, detail the imperial and daily activities at the abbey until 1030 CE. The account is supplemented by a chronicle of global history that includes Biblical events, placing Quedlinburg in a longer Christian history. Details of events such as church consecrations, imperial visits, and feast days are present throughout the chronicle. Of particular interest is the interaction between the Holy Roman Emperor and his court with the nuns at Quedlinburg, many of whom were noble or royal family members. The Ottonian dynasty was particularly close to Quedlinburg, ensuring Imperial favor in the area. Thus, the text is valuable as a historical source for the region around Quedlinburg in the eleventh century, the imperial court, and the daily life at the Abbey. The text contains the first mention of Lithuania, and is considered a fairly accurate source for relations between the Empire and northeastern cultures in the eleventh century. Scholars believe that the annalist was a woman, probably one of the nuns at Quedlinburg. Other chronicles in the area utilize the Annals as a source, demonstrating the text's influence and readership beyond the walls of the nunnery.

Date Range: 1008 CE - 1030 CE

Region: Quedlinburg and Surroundings

Region tags: Germany, Western Europe, Quedlinburg

The area around Quedlinburg, Germany, and its local sphere of influence.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Christian Popp, "Die Quedlinburger Kirchweihe im Jahre 1021: Neue Überlegungen zum altbekannten Weihebericht in den Annales Quedlinburgenses," *Deutsches Archiv für Erforschung des Mittelalters* 72:2 (2016): 469-499.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/tmr/article/view/16073/22191>
- Source 1 Description: Felice Lifshitz, "Review of Giese, ed., *Annales Quedlinburgenses*," *The Medieval Review* (2006)

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: https://www.dmgh.de/mgh_ss_rer_germ_72/index.htm#page/577/mode/1up
- Source 1 Description: Edition of the Latin text: Martina Giese. Die Annales Quedlinburgenses. MGH SS rer Germ 72. Hannover: Hahnsche Buchhandlung, 2004.
- Source 1 URL: https://www.dmgh.de/mgh_ss_3/index.htm#page/V/mode/1up
- Source 1 Description: Edition of the Latin text: Georgius Heinricus Pertz. Annales Quedlinburgenses. MGH SS 3; pp. 22-72. Hannover: Hahnsche, 1839.

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked
– with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Other textile: Vellum

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: Unknown

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Tomb
– No

↳ Cemetery

– No

↳ Temple

– No

↳ Shrine

– No

↳ Altar

– No

↳ Devotional marker

– No

↳ Cenotaph

– No

↳ Church

– No

↳ Mosque

– No

↳ Synagogue

– No

↳ Triumphal Arch

– No

↳ Monument

– No

↳ Mass Gathering Point

– No

↳ Cave(s)

– No

↳ Hilltops

– No

↳ Other natural sanctuaries

– No

↳ Boundary markers or lines

– No

↳ Domestic contexts

– No

↳ Library/archive

– Yes

Notes: The manuscript survives in a 16th century copy in Dresden, where it is digitized:
<https://digital.slub-dresden.de/en/workview/dlf/2891/1>

↳ Specify

– Specify: The manuscript survives in a 16th century copy in the Saxon State and University Library in Dresden, Germany.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: The Annals were probably created by the nuns living at Quedlinburg Abbey. Although many had familial ties to the Holy Roman Emperor, the Annals themselves were not funded by the imperial family but meant to be for the Abbey itself.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Most readers were probably the nuns at Quedlinburg Abbey in the centuries after its composition. Visiting officials and scholars probably also read portions of the text, as some pieces of the history are copied into other chronicles.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?

– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on

the matter?
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: The text does not include any of these items.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: There are some references to the Christian God and the Holy Spirit.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

Notes: The Annals record various events such as feasts, church consecrations, and battles. While these are not necessarily meant to be entertainment, they do provide insight into the people and places involved.

↳ Drama?

– No

↳ Comedy?

– No

↳ Tragedy?

– No

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Nuns at Quedlinburg Abbey wrote the text in the early 11th century. While some nuns were related by blood to the imperial family, others were from noble families around Germany.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Scribes at Quedlinburg probably copied and recopied the original manuscript, which is now lost.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The original manuscript of the Annals does not survive, but it was not targeted for specific destruction. The only existing copy is a 16th-century version in Dresden.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Notes: The Annals record several conflicts that occurred in Western Europe before 1030, with emphasis on Christians versus pagans or other groups, such as Charlemagne against Muslim forces. All of the mentioned warfare is meant to celebrate Christian victories against others, connecting Quedlinburg's history with longer narratives of good versus evil.

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Annals of Quedlinburg, Popp, Christian. "Die Quedlinburger Kirchweihe Im Jahre 1021: Neue Überlegungen Zum Altbekannten Weihebericht in Den Annales Quedlinburgenses", *Deutsches Archiv für Erforschung des Mittelalters*, 72.2 (2016).

Reference: Annals of Quedlinburg, Hahn, Cynthia. "Relics and Reliquaries: The Construction of Imperial Memory and Meaning, with Particular Attention to Treasuries at Conques, Aachen, and Quedlinburg", Vol. *Representing History, 900-1300: Art, Music, History*. University Park, PA: Penn State University Press, 2010.

Reference: Annals of Quedlinburg, Lifshitz, Felice. "Review to Giese, *Annales Quedlinburgenses*" *The Medieval Review* (2006). <https://scholarworks.iu.edu/journals/index.php/tmr/article/view/16073/22191>.